

DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF PREPARING STUDENTS FOR INDEPENDENT FAMILY LIFE THROUGH THE MEANS OF NATIONAL VALUES

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Abstract. *The fact that the issue of preparing young people for family life in educational institutions is an urgent problem in today's globalization process, the formation of an environment of healthy families by preparing young people for family life, the prevention of divorce between families has been considered as a result of socio-psychological research.*

Keywords: *family, preparation of young people for the Family, national values, early marriage, early childbirth visions of the family.*

Turning to our boys and girls, I want to say: look at marriage, family, the fate of the child with extremely deep responsibility. Take a superficial approach to this issue and do not risk the life of either yourself or another person. I believe that neighborhood activists, venerable kaywanis, devotees of our spirituality and religion who have seen a lot in this regard, and our young people who are becoming an example to their peers will try to get out of one collar. Sh.Mirziyoyev President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan[1].

At the next time, all the necessary conditions and opportunities are being created for the growth of the young generation in our country as fully mature, educated, intelligent and resourceful individuals with both deep knowledge and any profession.

It is also important to focus on the comprehensive health of the future spouses in order to find a healthy lifestyle among the population, especially among our young people, to take matters of family and marriage seriously, in this regard, first of all, to avoid various disappointments in the future.

Being the legal basis for preparing young people for family life, articles 76-80 of Chapter XIV of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan dedicated to the family, which is considered our main law, will be noted as the basis of all family legal relations[2]. In particular, in Article 76, the family is the main branch of society and it is under the protection of society and the state. Marriage is based on the traditional family values of the people of Uzbekistan, voluntary consent and equal rights of the married. The state creates social, economic, legal and other conditions for the full-fledged development of the family.

Article 77 obliges parents and their replacements to take care of their children until they reach adulthood, their upbringing, education, healthy, full-fledged and comprehensive maturation. The state and society ensure the feeding, upbringing, education of orphans and children deprived of the guardianship of their parents, their education, healthy, full-fledged and comprehensively maturing, encouraging charitable activities for this purpose.

Article 78 states that children are equal before the law, regardless of the parentage and civil status of their parents. It is the obligation of the state to ensure and protect the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of the child, to create the best conditions for his full-fledged development, physical, mental and cultural.

Article 79 states that the state ensures the protection of the personal, political, economic, social, cultural, environmental rights of young people, encourages their active participation in the life of society and the state. The state provides conditions for the formation and development of young people intellectually, creatively, physically and morally, for the implementation of their rights to education, health, housing, employment, employment and Recreation.

Article 80, adult working children are obliged to take care of their parents.

These rules are also found out by married persons in the system of continuing education in higher education institutions, starting from preschool educational organizations. In particular, such subjects and courses of study as "Alphabet of the Constitution", "lessons of the Constitution", "fundamentals of the Constitution", "foundations of State and law", "constitutional law", "jurisprudence" are taught.

The Family Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the legal grounds for preparing married people for family life. Family legal institutions such as marriage regulated by the Family Code, rights and obligations of spouses, termination of marriage, rights and obligations of parents and underage children, alimony obligations are important in increasing the legal awareness and culture of young married couples.

In Professional educational institutions and academic lyceums there is a club "Qizlarjon", a club "boy's club". While the plan of these clubs does not specify individual points for preparing students for family life in the spirit of national values, work is underway to prepare them for family life by forming socio-spiritual views.

On the preparation of students for family life in educational institutions, in 2018-2022, special educational courses, optional courses were analyzed.

Including: 40 hours are allocated for the subject "fundamentals of State and law" (in the academic year 2021-2022), 20 hours are taught in the 1st year. In course 1, there are no topics on the issue of preparing for family life within the framework of the topic. In course 2, the subject of Family Law is passed and the constitutional basis of family law through the subject. Family Code Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan. Relations regulated by family legislation. Subjects of family law. Equal rights of citizens in family relations. The procedure and conditions for concluding a marriage. The procedure for concluding a marriage. The volition of marriage. Marriage age. Cases that make it moneylogical to make a marriage. Medical examination of married persons. personal rights and obligations of the couple. The emergence of double rights and obligations. Equal rights of husband and wife in the family.

The right of husband and wife to choose a surname. The couple's solution to the issues of child education and family marriage. The type of training of the husband and wife, the rights to choose a profession and accommodation. Property rights and obligations of husband and wife. Common property of husband and wife. The fact that the husband and wife own, use and dispose of common property. Property of each of the husband and wife. Items of personal use of husband and wife. Division of the common property of the husband and wife. Determination of shares in the division of the common property of a husband and wife. Contractual procedure for husband and wife property. Marriage contract. Conclusion of a marriage contract. The content of the marriage contract. Change and terminate the marriage contract. Finding a marriage contract invalid. Grounds for termination of marriage. Detailed information on the procedure for separation from marriage is provided.

In academic lyceums, a special course was held on "Family Psychology" (issues of studying the rules of the declaration on the Prevention of domestic violence, the elimination of the use of violence against women) (in the 2018-2019 academic year).

The special course consists of 12 hours, according to the plan, the psychology of communication in the family, the psychology of conflicts in the family. Divorce, its causes and consequences. Fight against domestic violence. Topics of legal norms of abusive treatment of women in the family are included.

In academic lyceums and professional educational institutions, a special course on the "basics of reproductive health" was held (in the academic year 2021-2022).

A special course is allocated for 16 hours, in which the importance of passing a medical examination, prevention of early marriage and Inter-kin marriage. Topics such as family planning are included.

Also, on the topic of preparing young people for family life in higher education institutions, the optional course "etiquette of Oriental girls" consists of 6 hours (in the academic year 2019-2020), the role of the family in the upbringing of a girl in this course. Interpretation of the issue of raising a girl in the legacy of Islam and Eastern thinkers. Methods and means of forming national, universal, moral, aesthetic values in the upbringing of girls. Topics such as Girl hygiene are included.

The optional course "foundations of a healthy family" was held (in the academic year 2022-2023). The role of youth education in ensuring family strength in a total of 8-hour course. Methods and means of forming national, universal, moral, values in the formation of spiritual culture in young people. The health of a student-youth at the age of marriage as a key factor in family strength. A healthy lifestyle requires proper nutrition. Family judgments are the causes and consequences of their origin. The impact of the globalization process on the formation of the worldview of young people. Problematic diseases that occur among young people. Topics of benefits of pre-nikox medical examination are included.

In Module 6 of the educational program "fundamentals of medical knowledge", topics on the protection of motherhood and childhood are included (in the 2019-2020 academic year). Including mental-nervous disorders in children in topic 27. Hereditary diseases and developmental defects. Medical qualities of sexual education. The concept of Doyali assistance. Topic 28 the state of health of children and adolescents. Topics such as the Prevention of Balalar diseases are included.

When analyzing these training courses, the main focus is to see a medical approach to preparing young people for family life. The main emphasis is on reproductive health, which does not include issues of family Economy, family budgeting, national values in family preparation.

On the issue of preparing young people for family life, the decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of December 31, 2020 No. 820 "on measures for the further development of the Family Institute and the preparation of young people for Family Life" approved the regulation on the organization of the activities of Centers for preparing young people for family life.

Centers are provided to be organized under the district (city) family and women departments, they are assigned the following tasks:

to instill in the minds of the matrimonial people the exemplary form of the modern family and the conceptual ideas of "Family – Holy", "healthy family - healthy society", "family - in the protection of society and the state" and "prosperous family – the basis of the prosperity of society;

systematic training of married persons on issues of family-legal relations, psychology of family life, family economy and budget, foundations of reproductive health, strengthening of spiritual and moral values;

to ensure the strength of families, to prevent family divorces, to respect family values in married individuals, to create a healthy spiritual and moral environment in families, and to form the skills of being an instructive parent.

In the centers, it is established that married persons who have applied to the registry office for marriage and received consent to participate in training will be taught free of charge on the basis of a program with a training load of no less than 16 hours.

While the establishment of these centers sets out the state policy on the issue of preparing young people for family life, it is the participation of married persons who applied to the registry office for marriage and whose consent was received to participate in training sessions, which determines that the results in these courses will not be high.

The reason: first of all, this is the training of young people of marriage age in the centers (it is the married persons who applied to the registry office for marriage and whose consent was received to participate in training sessions, not more than 30 years old). The issue of preventing premature marriage and premature labor remains open due to the fact that the center-going listeners have reached the age of marriage of young people;

secondly, the fact that these courses are short-term does not allow the formation of skills of young people about preparing for family life in this term;

thirdly, the lack of special training of educators in mazur centers, the involvement of educators in educational institutions with leisurely classroom hours also indicate that the quality of education in the Centers is low.

It remains relevant in the following years, when the number of family deductions does not decrease. Cases of recorded marriages ending in divorce have not declined .

One in three family divorces date back to the first ten years of marriage and more.

Every year, more than half of the appeals to the courts for the annulment of marriage are being winged.

These judgments include family shortages, housing problems, inappropriate interference of parents and other relatives in family relationships, incompatibility of the character of husband and wife, one of which is due to harmful habits (drinking, drug abuse, etc.).k) many reasons, such as obsession, lead to family convictions.

The following measures should be prescribed to eliminate problems related to cases of early marriage and early childbirth, as well as family divorces:

development of proposals for improving regulatory legal documents on the Prevention of family decisions, ensuring the strength of families and strengthening their social protection;

improvement of the procedure for medical examination of students of general secondary education school, academic Lyceum and vocational schools;

development of a unified methodology for calculating data on early marriage, early childbirth and family decisions by age, as well as studying the general public opinion on issues related to these problems;

development and establishment of a special medical information and educational portal aimed at enhancing the medical culture of the population in the field of reproductive health, including adolescents, young brides and parents;

through the media, the conduct of akhbrot-propaganda work aimed at broad coverage among the population of the negative consequences of early marriage and early childbirth among teenage girls, as well as the negative impact of family decisions on childbearing.

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